

application and resists lodging. It is relatively tolerant of low temperature at meiosis and flowering. Leaves are light green and become yellowish-green during ripening. It has had few disease and insect problems. Yield is comparatively stable.

Hang Feng has superior grain quality and high milling percentage. Milled rice is broad, uniform, and white, with good flavor, suitable stickiness, good scent, and glossy appearance.

The variety is most commonly planted as a second crop (plant height 70-75 cm),

although it also is single-cropped (plant height 85-90 cm). Second crop growth duration is 140 d. A single crop takes about 160 d. Hang Feng yields about 5 t/ha as a second crop and may yield 30% more in a single-cropping system. *ℳ*

Performance of BW rices in the midcountry wet zone of Sri Lanka

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We evaluated 5 short-duration (90-100 d) BW rices for performance in the Sri Lanka midcountry wet zone (MZ) at Peradeniya in Jul-Oct 1982. BW272-6B, BW288-2, BW293-2, BW267-3, and BW267-7 were developed by the Bombuwela Regional Agricultural Research Station (BRARS) for the low country wet zone, mainly the Kalutara Galle and Matara districts.

Plant height, 1,000-grain weight, yield, number of productive tillers, and panicle length in the MZ were compared with similar data from BRARS, where the varieties were grown in Apr-Jun 1982 (see table). Fertilizer doses were the same at both sites.

Peradeniya is 490 m above sea level and Bombuwela is 3 m above sea level. Average monthly temperature and rainfall at the sites are in the figure. The

Performance of BW rices at Peradeniya and BRARS.^a

Variety	Plant ht (cm)		Productive tillers (no.)		Panicle length (cm)		1000-grain wt (g)		Grain wt per plant	
	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B
BW 272-6B	102.8	100.5	2.4	5.0	25.6	26.36	16.1	16.7	4.02	5.75
BW 288-2	52.3	66.51	3.3	4.0	16.1	20.4	27.7	29.8	4.78	8.60
BW 293-2	59.0	66.01	1.9	3.0	9.5	22.8	27.2	30.0	3.21	7.80
BW 267-3	75.8	77.09	2.1	5.0	22.1	20.08	30.1	30.6	4.49	9.20
BW 266-7	94.0	81.56	2.2	4.0	21.8	21.71	25.4	25.8	2.03	5.68

^a P = av of 60 plants (20/replication) were analyzed at Peradeniya. B = data obtained from BRARS.

Monthly precipitation and temperature in Bombuwela and Peradeniya, Sri Lanka. 1982.

soil at Peradeniya is an alluvial gley.

The varieties performed poorly in the MZ, and took longer to mature than at BRARS. BW272-6B, normally a 90-d variety, matured in 122 d. All the varieties retained their insect and diseases resistance. BW267-3 yielded highest at both sites.

The differences in yield and maturity may have been caused by differences in location, that could have attributed to differences in humidity, sunshine hours, rainfall, day-night temperature, and irrigation water quality. *ℳ*

Manhar, high yielding, early maturing rice for the irrigated plains of Uttar Pradesh

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Manhar (UPR103-44-2) was developed using the pedigree method after hybridization of IR24 and Cauvery. It is a semidwarf that matures in 123 d, and is suitable for the irrigated plains of Uttar Pradesh.

Table 1. Mean performance of Manhar in trials in Uttar Pradesh, India.

Trial ^a	Year	Mean yield (t/ha)			
		Manhar	Saket 4 (check)	Prasad (check)	Increase ^b (%) over check
VT-Early	1980	5.1	4.3	4.2	18
VT-Early	1981	4.5	—	4.3	3
VT-Early	1982	4.9	—	4.1	20
VT-Early	1983	4.6	—	4.3	5
VT-Early	1984	4.8	—	4.4	10
SVT-Early	1982	4.8	3.9	—	22
SVT-Early	1983	4.3	3.7	—	15
SVT-Early	1984	3.7	3.2	—	18
PVT-2 (AICRIP)	1982	4.9	3.3	Ratna	49
PTV-2 (AICRIP)	1983	3.1	2.3	Rasi	34
Mean Sites (no.)		4.6	3.9	4.2	
		61	29	33	

^a VT = Varietal Trials, SVT = Standard Varietal Trials, PVT = All India Coordinated Trials. ^b Mean of 17% over Saket 4, 8% over Prasad.

Table 2. Distinguishing morphological characters Manhar, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Character	Particulars
Height	88 cm
Seedling vigor	Good
Lodging	Resistant
Plant type	Dwarf, ideal
Leaf sheath	Green
Tillering	Good (14 tillers/plant)
Position of flag leaf	Erect
Photoperiod sensitivity	Photoperiod insensitive
Panicle length	21 cm
Apiculus	Green
Duration	120 d from seed to seed
No. of grains/panicle	165
1,000 grain weight	19.9 g
Grain type	Long slender
Cooking quality	Good

Manhar yielded consistently more than Saket 4 and Prasad in kharif Varietal Trials-Early, Standard Varietal Trials-Early, and All India Coordinated trials throughout Uttar Pradesh (Table 1). Manhar yielded 17% higher than Saket 4 and 8% higher than Prasad. With optimum agronomic management, it yielded 6 t/ha at Pantnagar in 1983.

Manhar is moderately resistant to bacterial leaf blight and has field tolerance to whitebacked planthopper. Its grain is long and slender with good cooking quality. Table 2 gives distinguishing morphological characteristics. *ℒ*

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HPU8020, a promising mutant rice

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HPU8020 was isolated 1973 from Bala, an early-maturing rice that was treated with 20 Kr gamma rays. HPU8020 matures 10-13 d later than Bala. Unlike Bala, it has synchronous tillering and anthocyanin pigmentation at the plant base.

HPU8020 has significantly greater plant height, panicles/plant, panicle length, panicle weight, and 1,000-grain weight, and yields more than Bala (Table 1). Although it matures later, it has

Table 1. Agronomic and quality characteristics of HPU8020 and parent variety Bala, Himachal Pradesh, India.

Characteristic	Bala	HPU8020
Plant height (cm)	71.8	74.8
Panicles/plant (no.)	5	8
Panicle length (cm)	19	20
Panicle weight (g)	2.8	3
Spikelets/panicle	142	155
1000-grain wt (g)	21	22
Sterility (%)	17	14
Yield/plant (g)	12	17
Plant efficiency (yield/plant per d)	0.12	0.14
Panicle density		9.46
Grain length:breadth		2.02
Protein (%)		7.26
Chlorophyll content at flowering (mg/g fresh wt)		1.24
Chlorophyll a:b		0.74
Leaf area index		1.09

Table 2. Grain yield of HPU8020 in Himachal Pradesh, India, 1976-80.

Year	HP118020		IR579 (check)	
	Yield (t/ha)	Sites (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Sites (no.)
1976	4.3	5	3.9	5
1977	4.7	10	4.4	10
1978	4.9	7	4.3	4
1979	4.4	4	3.0	4
1980	5.8	4	4.9	4
Mean	4.8		4.2	

Table 3. Grain yield of HPU8020 in All India Coordinated trials.

Year	Sites (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	
		HPU8020 (IET5878)	Cauvery
<i>Direct seeded rainfed trials</i>			
1978	16	3.3	2.9
1979	14	3.3	2.9
1980	30	3.2	2.8
1981	17	2.4	2.3
<i>Transplanted experiments</i>			
1978	6	3.5	3.2
1979	8	5.0	4.8
1980	13	3.9	3.6
1981	17	4.1	3.7

higher plant efficiency than its parent. HPU8020 has short, bold grains like Bala, with 7.26% protein content.

In yield trials from 1976 to 1980 at altitudes below 900 m in Himachal Pradesh, HPU8020 yielded an average 4.8 t/ha; 14% more than IR579, a high yielding semidwarf (Table 2). HPU8020 (IET5878) was evaluated throughout

India in the All India Coordinated Rice Trials from 1978 to 1981. In direct-seeded rainfed conditions. HPU8020 yielded an average 3.1 t/ha, 13% more than Cauvery, the check variety (Table 3). It yielded highest. 7.3 t/ha, at Sabour in 1979. HPU8020 flowers in 84 d, vs 77 for Cauvery.

In transplanted trials, HPU8020 yielded an average 4.1 t/ha, 10%, more than Cauvery (Table 3). It yielded highest. 8 t/ha. at Bikaner in 1979, compared to 7 t/ha for Cauvery. In transplanted experiments, HPU8020 flowered in 88 d, vs 83 d for Cauvery.

HPU8020 has strong blast resistance and resistance to gall midge, stem borer, and green leafhopper.

It has been released for general cultivation in Pondicherry, India, and identified for All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Program minikit trials in south and southeast India in rabi. It has been nominated for release for general cultivation in low altitude areas of Himachal Pradesh. *ℒ*

Ethyl methane sulfonate (EMS) induced rice mutants

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Randhunipagal is a tall (150 cm), aromatic, indica rice with 150-160 d maturity. We exposed unhusked